

CORRECTION

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Correction: The advantages and challenges of non-invasive towed PILOT tags for free-ranging deep-diving megafauna

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Following publication of the original article [1], the authors noticed the following errors in the citation of tables and figures under Results section and the captions of Figs. 6, 7 and 8:

In subsection, “Drag and stability”, the citation of Table 2 should be Table 1;

In subsequent section, “Whale shark (*R. typus*)”, the citation of Fig. 5A and B should be replaced by Fig. 6A and B;

In section, “Tiger shark (*G. cuvier*) (towed vs fixed)”, the citation of Fig. 6 should be replaced by Fig. 7; last sentence mention Fig. 7 should be replaced by Fig. 8; reference to Additional File 8 should be eliminated.

Figure 6 legend should be replaced by “Surging acceleration, depth and speed, **A** a 35 min Yo-Yo behaviour segment of a 8500 cm whale-shark, **B** detail of the section delimited by the black rectangle in **A**. Warmer colours

in the spectrogram represent stronger signals, whereas cooler colours represent weaker signals.”

Figure 7 legend should be replaced by “Surging and swaying acceleration of a 230 cm tiger shark double-tagged with the i-Pilot **A** and an accelerometer/depth package attached to a pectoral fin **B**. Warmer colours represent stronger signals and cooler colours represent weaker signals. Lower panel represents the dive profile (m)”.

Figure 8 legend should read “Surging and swaying acceleration of a 230 cm tiger shark double tagged with i-Pilot **A** and accelerometer/depth package attached to a pectoral fin **B**. Warmer colours represent stronger signals and cooler colours represent weaker signals. Bottom panel represents the dive profile (m).

Figures 5 and 6 should have A on the top panel and B on the bottom panel.

The original article [1] has been corrected.

The original article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40317-022-00310-1>.

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Fig. 5 Surging acceleration, depth, and speed over; **A** descent–ascent–descent swimming behaviour of a 280-cm blue shark, and **B** details of the section delimited by the black rectangle in A. Warmer colours in the spectrogram represent stronger signals, whereas cooler colours represent weaker signals

Fig. 6 Surging and swaying acceleration of a 230-cm tiger shark double-tagged with the i-Pilot (top) and an accelerometer/depth package attached to a pectoral fin (bottom). Warmer colours represent stronger signals and cooler colours represent weaker signals. Bottom panel represents the dive profile (m)

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Reference

1. Fontes J, Macena B, Solleliet-Ferreira S, Buyle F, Magalhães R, Bartolomeu T, Liebsch N, Meyer C, Afonso P. The advantages and challenges of non-invasive towed PILOT tags for free-ranging deep-diving megafauna. *Anim Biotelemetry*. 2022;10:39. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40317-022-00310-1>.

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